

A Study of Stressors on Parent Child Relationships

by

Natalie Albarran

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University of Honors Program
California State University Fullerton
July 2022

Approved by:

Date:

7/14/2022

Dr. Horn-Mallers, Department of Human Services

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Director, University Honors Program

INTRODUCTION

Familial Stress

The ability to identify stress in children is critical when attempting to define their ways of growth and development. The young adolescent brain is still only just on the cusp of the developmental state, their environments only serving to further influence how they handle their situations. A way to do this is by defining the stressors in question that are capable of disrupting their behaviors. By gathering the perspective of both parents and children equips a better understanding of the potential of a child having their stress levels be affected from a familial stand point. This can be categorized as a crossover event in which the behaviors exhibited by the parent have the potential to affect the behaviors of their child. This understanding of spillover and how it works is important in terms of parent-child relationships as knowing a parent's behavior can have such a strong impact on their child. Trying to manage their own stress can assist with both social development and how to best meet their child's behavior and emotional needs. Maintaining a healthy parent-child relationship and acknowledging this presence of a potential spillover happening between the two parties can assist with this being brought further into the light with its awareness. Understanding that stress in parent-child relationships assists with future relationships that the child will have, leading them to develop happy and content relationships. This affects their parent and child relationship, with having the capability to feel secure in their emotional and social development. This assists the family structure as a whole, having the ability to understand one another.

One would expect for those in their adolescent years to not experience stress, a simple idea stemming from the fact that the topic is most often associated with adults and teens. However, stressors in children are prevalent in their daily lives and are even said to be high (e.g., American Psychological Association 2012; Vanaelst et al. 2012). By gathering the perspective of both parents and children equips a better understanding of the potential of a child having their stress levels be affected from a familial stand point. This can be categorized as a spillover event in which the behaviors exhibited by the parent have the potential to affect the behaviors of their child. Previous research has also discussed a demographic of how stress is seen in adolescence, specifically through girls and older children, as well as a higher amount of stress being reported on weekdays rather than weekends (Suarez-Morales & Lopez, 2009). From the findings, there was also a discussion on stress being variable in nature with the diary reporting and the countless ways in which children can view situations as stress. This includes school and other familial activities. However, it opened up the further possibility of looking into the effects of spillover between parent and child relationships as well as further health symptoms to correlate with this documentation of stress.

Latinex, low-income communities

Previous research on this topic has focused on the levels of stress with respect to economic or sociocultural stressors. These sociocultural factors relating to the effects of discrimination against those in the Latinex communities and children internally visualizing these reactions from their parents as a response (Mendoza et. al, 2017). The economic aspect relates to the stresses of maintaining stable living income while being put in an obviously lower income environment. Such spilling down towards the adolescence once again potentially internalizing these reactions that their parents may give them in regards to their situation. Low income families' response to stress can impact family dynamics as well as differ between mothers and fathers. Addressing these economic stressors specific to those of a minority group can also provide further insight to another aspect of stress that is not often viewed in this form of research. An aspect that can highlight another group faced with these difficulties.

Chronic financial stress can lead to a hindrance in things such as relationship quality, parenting practices, and mental health. Such factors that not only affect the mentioned family dynamic but create poorer parent and child relationships. Previous studies have found that parents who reported more responses towards financial stress are at risk for poorer psychosocial functioning. Parents noted to have higher levels of social support and indicated to have lower levels of stress as a result of this (Perzow et. al, 2018). The number of individuals and facilities offered aid to these families in part provides a substantial benefit to the lingering pressure on their own mental health.

METHODOLOGY

Daily Interviews

Consent and assent forms were completed with the parents and children at the children's school during an initial start-up meeting. Children were told that our research team was interested in talking with them about what goes on in their life and that sometimes we all experience things that causes frustration or challenges, or even excitement and that we wanted to learn more about this. Children were also told that they did not have to answer anything that made them feel uncomfortable, that they could tell us if they did not want to talk or share, and that they could end their participation in the study if they wanted to. All of this was explained to parents as well at this time. During this same meeting, a research assistant explained the daily diary procedure to the participants and talked to the mothers individually about their daily schedules to determine the optimal time for daily interviews. Participants were then interviewed

daily for five days beginning on Thursday and ending on Monday. These days were chosen so that we could reduce burden of participation and so that we could capture varying experiences occurring on both weekdays and weekends. Interviews were conducted over the phone between 5pm and 8pm by a research assistant. Typically, mothers were interviewed first, and then the participating children were interviewed. All participants were asked to complete their interviews away from other family members so that they could speak freely. The focus of this study is on children's outcomes. The study included 25 children between 8 and 10 years of age.

Measures

A structured interview was used to measure the daily experience of stressors as well as physical health symptoms and mood. Every day, children were asked to think back since the last time they had talked to the researcher or, if it was the first interview, since about that same time the night before.

RESULTS

Child age was positively related to both average number of daily stressors reported ($r = .46, p = .02$), and average number of aches and pains reported ($r = .41, p = .05$), such that older children tended to report more than younger children. In terms of stress categories, older children were more likely to report performance related stressors, ($r = .44, p = .03$) than younger children. When more data is collected, relationships between demographic data (SES, parent education level, race/ethnicity) and stressors will be explored.

The first goal of the current study was to explore and describe children's daily experiences of stress. Based on five daily reports of the 24-item measure, children could report up to 120 total stressors for the study period. Over the course of the 5-day study period, children reported between 7 and 55 total stressors with an average of 33.0 stressful events reported ($SD = 12.2$). Per day, out of 24 stressful events children reported between 0 and 16 stressors, with an average report of 6.6 stressors ($SD = 2.4$) per day. Of the 25 children in the sample, two children (8%) reported an average of more than 10 stressors per day, while two children reported less than 2 stressors per day on average. Looking at individual items, the most commonly endorsed stressor was "needing a ride from parents" which was reported by 13.8 (55.2%) kids per day, on average. The two other most commonly endorsed stressors were "finding something too easy or boring", and "getting school grades back", which were both reported by 11.8 (47.4%) children per day on average. "Being teased" was the least endorsed stressor, reported by an average of 1.2 (4.8%) kids per day. Further, "losing a privilege" and "thinking about how you look" were uncommonly endorsed as well, reported by less than 10% of children per day (8.8 and 9.6%, respectively). Figure 1 shows the average number of days that children reported each individual stressor. When examining children's stressors by category, children most commonly endorsed performance-related stressors, reporting an average of 2.0 stressors per day out of six total items (33%), and stressors related to perceptions of control, with an average of 1.4 stressors per day

(28% of 5 items). Interpersonal related stress was also common, with children reporting an average of 1.6 interpersonal stressors per day (26% of six items). Less common were time management and wellness stressors, with children reporting less than one stressor in each category per day.

DISCUSSION

The future of this research allows for the improvement of current child relationship quality. Understanding what is affecting the parent trickles down to better parenting for the child to experience. Ways to combat this stress through its acknowledgment can allow for more awareness of these issues and relieve it in a way that benefits the parent's mental health. This will then alleviate the amount of stress the child may receive from the household by tackling one of the sources that this stress may stem from. Parents noted to have higher levels of social support and indicated to have lower levels of stress as a result of this (Perzow et. al, 2018). Impacting the ways children experience stress is of great importance to the overall mental health of the child as well considering the number of obstacles they are more likely to face later on. Previous studies have shown that measuring HRV in even something short as 5-minute parameters can indicate if an individual is dealing with chronic stress (Michels et.al, 2013). Having something such as HRV or cortisol levels as a form of measurement serves to provide the objective standpoint of the topic of focus (De Witte et al, 2016). Future studies should utilize physiological indicators of stress, such as cortisol or heart rate variability, to obtain an objective approach to the documentation of their stresses, in addition to self-reports via interviews.

References

- Burkhart, M. L., Horn Mallers, M., & Bono, K. E. (2017). Daily reports of stress, mood, and physical health in middle childhood. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 26(5), 1345–1355. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-017-0665-0>.
- De Witte, N. A., Sütterlin, S., Braet, C., & Mueller, S. C. (2016). Getting to the Heart of Emotion Regulation in Youth: The Role of Interoceptive Sensitivity, Heart Rate Variability, and Parental Psychopathology. *PloS one*, 11(10), e0164615. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0164615>.

- Mendoza, M. M., Dmitrieva, J., Perreira, K. M., Hurwich-Reiss, E., & Watamura, S. E. (2017). The effects of economic and sociocultural stressors on the well-being of children of Latino immigrants living in poverty. *Cultural Diversity & Ethnic Minority Psychology*, 23(1), 15–26. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cdp0000111>.
- Michels, N., Sioen, I., Clays, E., De Buyzere, M., Ahrens, W., Huybrechts, I., Vanaelst, B., & De Henauw, S. (2013). Children's heart rate variability as stress indicator: Association with reported stress and Cortisol. *Biological Psychology*, 94(2), 433–440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsycho.2013.08.005>.
- Perzow, S., Bray, B. C., & Wadsworth, M. E. (2018). Financial stress response profiles and psychosocial functioning in low-income parents. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 32(4), 517–527. <https://doi.org/10.1037/fam0000403>.
- Silvetti, M. S., Drago, F., & Ragonese, P. (2001). Heart rate variability in healthy children and adolescents is partially related to age and gender. *International Journal of Cardiology*, 81(2-3), 169–174. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-5273\(01\)00537-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-5273(01)00537-x).
- Speer, K. E., Semple, S., Naumovski, N., & McKune, A. J. (2020). Measuring heart rate variability using commercially available devices in healthy children: A validity and Reliability Study. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 10(1), 390–404. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe10010029>.

Suarez-Morales, L., & Lopez, B. (2009, April 29). *The impact of acculturative stress and daily hassles on pre-adolescent psychological adjustment: Examining anxiety symptoms.* *Journal of Primary Prevention, 30*, 335-349.